

Theoretical estimation of thermodynamic properties of molten salt mixtures by Flory's statistical theory[†]

Vinay Sanguri* and Nidhi Singh

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : drvsanguri@rediffmail.com; nidhisinghh@gmail.com

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Abstract : The field of molten salts and their mixtures has been a subject of renewed research over the past few decades and has attracted the attention of scientists and technologists from such diverse fields as theoretical and applied electrochemistry, inorganic chemistry, co-ordination chemistry, thermo chemistry, fuel cells and batteries, corrosive science, the principle of liquid structure, theoretical physics and chemistry. In the present work, keeping in mind the importance of molten salt mixtures, Flory's statistical theory has been employed for the computation of ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), internal pressure (P_i), thermal expansion coefficient (α), isothermal compressibility (β_T), adiabatic compressibility (β_S), heat capacity at constant pressure (C_p), heat capacity at constant volume (C_v), heat capacities ratio (γ), pseudo-Gruneisen parameter (Γ), excess volume (V^E), excess heat capacity at constant pressure (C_p^E) and non-linearity parameter (B/A) for various molten salt systems.

Keywords : Thermodynamic properties, Flory's statistical theory, theoretical estimation.

Introduction

A critical review of various aspects of molten salts and their mixtures is given by Lumsden¹, Janz² and Bockris³. The behaviour of molten salts has been explained on the basis of various models including vacant model, the hole model, the crystalline model, the polyhedral model, the free-volume model, the significant structure model and the principle of corresponding states. A critical discussion of various properties of molten salts and their mixtures, and their theoretical estimation has been presented in 1982⁴ and 1983⁵. Sternberg *et al.*⁶⁻⁸ presented comprehensive studies of thermodynamic properties of a number of pure and binary molten salts by measuring sound velocity, density and surface tension. Rigid hard sphere theory advanced by Reiss, Frish, Helfand and Lebowitz^{9,10} has been applied by Mayer and Reiss^{11,12} to establish interrelationship among thermal expansivities, surface tensions and compressibilities for molten salts. Misdolea and Vilcu¹³ used significant structure theory to evaluate heat capacities, compressibilities and thermal expansivities of some molten alkali halides. Pandey *et al.* used Flory's statistical theory and cellular

hole model to evaluate the surface tension of molten salts¹⁴ and binary molten salt mixtures¹⁵⁻¹⁸. Increasing importance of molten salts and their mixtures as well as the continuation of theoretical and experimental researches inspired the present investigator to undertake the studies of such systems.

In the present work we are applying Flory's theory for estimating the values of various thermodynamic properties of binary molten salts mixtures. In earlier approaches, ultrasonic velocity of liquid mixture has been calculated on the basis of Flory-Patterson theory in conjunction with Auerbach and Altenberg empirical relations. But in present approach, no empirical relation is used. Except mole fraction no other property of molten salt mixture is desired. As far as our knowledge is concerned, nobody has, so far, succeeded in estimating the various thermodynamic properties viz. ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), internal pressure (P_i), thermal expansion coefficient (α), isothermal compressibility (β_T), adiabatic compressibility (β_S), heat capacity at constant pressure (C_p), heat capacity at constant volume (C_v), heat capacities ratio (γ), pseudo-Gruneisen parameter (Γ), excess

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

volume (V^E), excess heat capacity at constant pressure (C_P^E) and non-linearity parameter (B/A) of molten salt mixtures using the most popular Flory theory without the help of any empirical relation which is very novel approach. All the above mentioned thermodynamic properties of any type of molten salts mixture can be predicted simply from the knowledge of α , β_T , C_P and V of pure components.

B/A is used as a parameter to describe the non-linearity of the medium. It can be obtained from the distortion of finite amplitude waves and the variation of sound velocity with temperature and pressure. From the knowledge of non-linearity parameter, one can gain information about some physical properties of the liquids such as internal pressure, intermolecular spacing, acoustic scattering and structural behavior etc. in liquids and liquid mixtures. The importance of the present work is that first time Flory theory is applied to calculate non-linearity parameter (B/A). In the calculation of non-linearity parameter (B/A) with the help of Flory statistical theory not any experimental data of molten salt mixtures is used.

Theoretical

From the knowledge of α , β_T and V of pure components, the values of $\tilde{V}$, V^* , P^* , $\bar{T}$ and T^* for pure components can be obtained. Segment fraction (ψ) and site fraction (θ) of liquid mixtures have been computed by the method suggested earlier¹⁹. With the help of segment and site fraction reduced volume, $\tilde{V}$, of the mixture is calculated by the method given by earlier workers¹⁹⁻²⁵.

The molar volume (V) of the mixture is related with the characteristic volume (V^*) and reduced volume ($\tilde{V}$) of the mixture as,

$$V = V^* \tilde{V} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{where } V^* = \sum x_i V_i^* \quad (2)$$

Density of the mixture is given by

$$\rho_m = \frac{M_m}{V} \quad (3)$$

where M_m is the molar mass of the mixture expressed as

$$M_m = \sum x_i M_i \quad (4)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction and M_i the molar mass of the i -th pure component. Eq. (3) in conjunction with eq. (1) can be used to compute ρ_m of the liquid mixture.

Isothermal compressibility of the liquid mixture can be calculated by the following expression :

$$\beta_T = \frac{\alpha T \tilde{V}^2}{P^*} \quad (5)$$

Thermal expansion coefficient of the mixture is obtained by the equation

$$\alpha = \frac{(\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1)}{T(1 - 3(\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1))} \quad (6)$$

Internal pressure (P_i) is related with the thermal expansion coefficient and isothermal compressibility through the relation

$$P_i = \frac{\alpha T}{\beta_T} \quad (7)$$

Heat capacity at constant pressure of the mixture is defined as

$$C_P = C_P^E + C_{P(\text{idl})} \quad (8)$$

where $C_{P(\text{idl})}$ is ideal heat capacity of the mixture and defined as

$$C_{P(\text{idl})} = \sum x_i C_{P,i} \quad (9)$$

where $C_{P,i}$ = heat capacity of i -th pure component. C_P^E is defined by Khanwalkar *et al.*²⁶ according to Flory theory, as

$$C_P^E = \frac{P^* V^*}{T^*} \left[\frac{1}{\left(\frac{4}{3}\tilde{V}^{-1/3} - 1\right)} - \sum \left\{ \frac{x_i}{\left(\frac{4}{3}\tilde{V}^{-1/3} - 1\right)} \right\} \right] \quad (10)$$

β_S is calculated with the help of well-known thermodynamic relation

$$\beta_S = \beta_T - \frac{\alpha^2 TV}{C_P} \quad (11)$$

Ultrasonic velocity (u) of the mixture is obtained with the help of following relation :

$$u = \left(\frac{1}{\beta_S \rho} \right)^{1/2} \quad (12)$$

The excess volume of the mixture is calculated with the help of eq. (18) of Ref. 24.

$$V^E = (\sum x_i V_i^*) \tilde{V}^E \quad (13)$$

Heat capacities ratio, γ , for the mixture can be calculated by the well known relation

$$\gamma = \frac{\beta_T}{\beta_S} \quad (14)$$

The heat capacity of mixture at constant volume (C_V) is computed by following relation :

$$C_V = C_P/\gamma \quad (15)$$

Pseudo-Gruneisen parameter (Γ) of the mixture can be calculated using the following relation :

$$\Gamma = \frac{\gamma-1}{\alpha T} \quad (16)$$

General formulation for the non-linearity parameter in terms of the acoustical parameters of liquids has been made using the expression for the sound velocity (u), and introducing the contribution due to isobaric acoustic parameters (K) and the isothermal acoustic parameter (K''). The expression for the calculation of B/A of mixture has been expressed as²⁷,

$$\frac{B}{A} = 2K + 2\gamma K'' \quad (17)$$

Computations of K and K'' require only the knowledge of thermal expansion coefficient, α . Detailed method of calculation is given in literature^{28,29}.

Results and discussion

The values of ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), internal pressure (P_i), thermal expansion coefficient (α), isothermal compressibility (β_T), adiabatic compressibility (β_S), heat capacity at constant pressure (C_P), heat capacity at constant volume (C_V), heat capacities ratio (γ), pseudo-Gruneisen parameter (Γ), excess volume (V^E),

excess heat capacity at constant pressure (C_P^E) and non-linearity parameter (B/A) for molten salt mixtures have been evaluated with the help of Flory's statistical theory at 1073 K and at different compositions of first salt of each pair. Following systems are studied in the present work : Binary molten salt systems : NaCl + KCl, NaCl + RbCl, NaCl + CsCl, KCl + RbCl, LiCl + KCl, KCl + KBr, LiCl + RbCl, LiCl + CsCl, RbCl + CsCl, KCl + CsCl, LiBr + RbBr, NaBr + RbBr, NaI + RbI, NaBr + KBr and KCl + NaI.

All the parameters of pure components are listed in Table 1. The necessary data needed, for the calculation, have been taken from different sources^{8,13,30}. Tables 2 and 3 enlist the computed and experimental values of all aforementioned properties of binary molten salts mixtures respectively. In Table 4, percentage deviation of molten salt mixtures has been presented.

For the comparison of theoretically computed values with the observed values under consideration, the experimental values of liquid mixtures were taken from different sources^{8,30-32}. The experimental values of β_S , C_P and C_V of molten salt mixtures were obtained by the following equations :

$$\beta_{S(\text{exp})} = \frac{\beta_{T(\text{exp})}}{\gamma(\text{exp})} \quad (18)$$

$$C_{P(\text{exp})} = \frac{u^2(\text{exp})\alpha^2(\text{exp})TM}{\gamma(\text{exp}) - 1} \quad (19)$$

Table 1. Parameters of pure molten salts at 1073 K

Components	V (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (K ⁻¹)	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	$\bar{V}$	P* (J cm ⁻³)	T* (K)	C _p (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
KCl	49.38	1.5100	0.386	38.40	1.3225	1886.89	15951.6	66.35
LiCl	29.83	1.4210	0.305	24.30	1.2673	2161.65	17911.0	63.24
RbCl	55.65	2.1730	0.406	44.50	1.3349	1742.21	15604.9	69.23
CsCl	63.97	2.6320	0.406	49.70	1.3349	1559.83	15604.9	74.27
RbBr	63.95	2.5860	0.414	53.40	1.3402	1494.16	15463.7	64.39
LiBr	37.00	2.3470	0.276	31.51	1.2460	1457.26	18911.4	42.56
RbI	77.45	2.7420	0.420	67.29	1.3439	1209.30	15369.3	61.39
NaI	57.47	2.6080	0.364	46.40	1.3079	1438.86	16398.3	66.43
NaBr	44.78	2.2980	0.355	35.30	1.3023	1832.20	16581.8	63.70
KBr	57.32	2.0760	0.380	43.80	1.3185	1618.35	16068.3	68.62
NaCl	37.60	1.5544	0.360	28.70	1.3053	2293.29	16480.2	66.94

Table 2. Computed values of thermodynamic properties of binary molten salt mixtures by Flory theory at 1073 K

x_1	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (K ⁻¹)	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	$\beta_S \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹)	C_P (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$P_1 \times 10^7$ (dyne cm ⁻²)	C_P^E (g cm ⁻³)	γ	u (m s ⁻¹)	Γ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	C_V (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	B/A
NaCl+KCl											
0.207	-0.0115	36.43	25.42	66.48	1122.76	0.0088	1.433	1609.86	1.058	46.40	7.515
0.512	-0.0183	33.48	23.76	66.67	1196.80	0.0134	1.409	1658.45	1.022	47.30	7.487
0.729	-0.0149	31.37	22.51	66.79	1257.75	0.0106	1.393	1698.15	0.997	47.94	7.469
NaCl+RbCl											
0.250	-0.0393	40.58	28.12	68.68	1044.86	0.0206	1.443	1313.68	1.046	47.58	7.541
0.500	-0.0545	36.63	25.80	68.12	1125.39	0.0273	1.420	1418.55	1.018	47.98	7.507
0.750	-0.0426	32.67	23.39	67.54	1223.64	0.0203	1.396	1558.29	0.992	48.36	7.476
NaCl+CsCl											
0.250	-0.0404	44.73	31.40	72.48	950.62	0.0422	1.424	1138.45	0.998	50.88	7.525
0.500	-0.0586	39.55	28.09	70.66	1046.66	0.0569	1.408	1261.99	0.986	50.18	7.499
0.750	-0.0479	34.19	24.57	68.82	1173.05	0.0432	1.391	1445.87	0.976	49.47	7.473
KCl+RbCl											
0.250	-0.0070	42.96	29.36	68.51	1000.87	0.0016	1.463	1297.84	1.077	46.83	7.565
0.500	-0.0094	41.43	28.41	67.79	1025.34	0.0021	1.459	1375.16	1.079	46.48	7.555
0.750	-0.0071	39.91	27.45	67.07	1051.31	0.0015	1.454	1467.65	1.082	46.13	7.545
LiCl+KCl											
0.200	-0.0529	35.80	25.54	65.77	1115.48	0.0418	1.402	1615.64	1.006	46.91	7.480
0.588	-0.0877	30.45	23.10	64.58	1205.84	0.0581	1.318	1714.95	0.867	48.98	7.395
0.704	-0.0776	28.77	22.21	64.21	1239.54	0.0485	1.295	1755.79	0.828	49.57	7.376
KCl+KBr											
0.200	0.0131	42.81	30.03	68.17	956.36	0.0063	1.425	1298.32	1.039	47.83	7.509
0.500	0.0204	41.24	28.75	67.49	998.09	0.0102	1.434	1384.88	1.055	47.06	7.519
0.600	0.0195	40.69	28.31	67.27	1013.05	0.0099	1.437	1418.10	1.061	46.80	7.522
0.800	0.0129	39.57	27.42	66.81	1044.70	0.0068	1.443	1492.75	1.072	46.29	7.529
LiCl+RbCl											
0.500	-0.1670	34.76	25.83	66.31	1111.26	0.0782	1.346	1420.59	0.895	49.28	7.426
LiCl+CsCl											
0.500	-0.2349	37.60	28.12	68.85	1030.22	0.0962	1.337	1254.84	0.870	51.49	7.421
RbCl+CsCl											
0.500	0.0067	47.19	32.47	71.76	922.57	0.0048	1.454	1128.61	1.042	49.37	7.563

Table 3. Experimental values of various thermodynamic properties of binary molten salt mixtures at 1073 K

x_1	ρ (exp)	u (exp)	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (exp)	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ (exp)	$\beta_S \times 10^{12}$ (exp)	$P_i \times 10^{-7}$ (exp)	C_p (exp)	γ (exp)	C_V (exp)	Γ (exp)
NaCl+KCl										
0.207	-	1572.48	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.512	-	1614.38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.729	-	1666.38	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NaCl+RbCl										
0.250	-	1283.60	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.500	-	1370.60	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.750	-	1515.40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
NaCl+CsCl										
0.250	-	1099.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.500	-	1224.40	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.750	-	1387.80	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
KCl+RbCl										
0.250	2.0207	1282.80	0.402	43.90	30.07	1013.80	67.75	1.460	46.41	1.067
0.500	1.8570	1358.60	0.397	42.00	29.17	1029.90	69.27	1.440	48.10	1.033
0.750	1.6850	1442.10	0.392	40.80	28.53	1107.70	68.56	1.430	47.94	1.023
LiCl+KCl										
0.200	1.4960	1585.40	0.375	37.50	26.60	1074.20	63.15	1.410	44.79	1.018
0.588	1.4620	1650.00	0.349	33.40	25.11	1119.50	59.82	1.330	44.98	0.883
0.704	1.4480	1696.00	0.338	31.20	24.00	1163.00	61.08	1.300	46.98	0.827
KCl+KBr										
0.200	-	1292.80	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.500	-	1347.20	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.600	-	1374.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.800	-	1488.00	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
LiCl-RbCl										
0.500	1.8950	1343.00	0.373	39.50	29.26	1007.40	62.82	1.350	46.53	0.880
LiCl-CsCl										
0.500	2.2060	1185.40	0.373	43.20	32.24	892.50	65.12	1.340	48.60	0.849
RbCl-CsCl										
0.500	2.4130	1113.50	0.406	48.80	33.42	982.00	68.92	1.460	47.21	1.056
KCl-CsCl										
0.500	2.1350	1206.70	0.397	46.00	32.17	-	69.59	1.430	48.67	1.010
LiBr-RbBr										
0.500	2.4780	1102.50	0.363	46.80	33.19	832.80	52.92	1.410	37.53	1.052
NaBr-RbBr										
0.500	2.4350	1129.10	0.390	46.70	32.21	895.80	61.99	1.450	42.75	1.076
NaI-RbI										
0.500	2.6460	962.10	0.396	59.20	40.83	717.80	62.69	1.450	43.24	1.059
NaBr-KBr										
0.100	-	1233.75	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.300	-	1242.52	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
0.700	-	1267.53	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4. The values of percentage deviations for various thermodynamic properties

x_1	% Deviation									
	α	β_T	β_S	P_i	C_p	γ	C_v	Γ	ρ	u
NaCl+KCl										
0.207	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-2.38
0.512	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-2.73
0.729	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-1.91
NaCl+RbCl										
0.250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-2.34
0.500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-3.50
0.750	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-2.83
NaCl+CsCl										
0.250	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-3.59
0.500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-3.07
0.750	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-4.18
KCl+RbCl										
0.250	0.27	2.14	2.35	1.28	-1.13	-0.21	-0.91	-0.95	-0.06	-1.17
0.500	0.23	1.36	2.61	0.44	2.13	-1.29	3.38	-4.49	-0.25	-1.22
0.750	0.15	2.18	3.79	5.09	2.17	-1.67	3.78	-5.75	-0.37	-1.77
LiCl+KCl										
0.200	0.85	4.52	3.97	-3.84	-4.14	0.57	-4.74	1.14	-0.27	-1.91
0.588	1.81	8.83	8.03	-7.71	-7.94	0.87	-8.89	1.79	-0.70	-3.94
0.704	1.73	7.80	7.47	-6.58	-5.13	0.36	-5.50	-0.15	-0.88	-3.53
KCl+KBr										
0.200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.43
0.500	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-2.80
0.600	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-3.21
0.800	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-0.32
LiCl-RbCl										
0.500	3.48	11.99	11.71	-10.31	-5.57	0.33	-5.91	-1.66	-1.22	-5.78
LiCl-CsCl										
0.500	3.28	12.96	12.76	-15.43	-5.73	0.22	-5.96	-2.48	-2.36	-5.86
RbCl-CsCl										
0.500	0.04	3.30	2.87	6.05	-4.12	0.44	-4.58	1.35	-0.22	-1.36
KCl-CsCl										
0.500	0.13	3.97	4.94	-	-1.05	-1.02	-0.03	-3.46	-0.40	-2.36
LiBr-RbBr										
0.500	2.05	6.32	6.37	-4.55	-1.35	-0.05	-1.30	-2.28	-0.95	-2.87
NaBr-RbBr										
0.500	1.09	5.25	4.60	-4.40	-3.34	24.29	-4.06	1.17	-1.49	-1.63
NaI-RbI										
0.500	0.92	4.33	3.93	-3.56	-1.96	0.42	-2.39	0.44	-1.61	-1.21
NaBr-KBr										
0.100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-1.61
0.300	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-1.61
0.700	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-1.18

$$C_{V(\text{exp})} = \frac{C_{P(\text{exp})}}{\gamma(\text{exp})} \quad (20)$$

In all the cases the calculated values of all the properties of binary molten salt mixtures by Flory's statistical theory show the same trend as observed experimentally. A careful study of Table 2 demonstrates that generally the computed values of ultrasonic velocity (u) and internal pressure (P_i) smoothly increase with increase in composition of 1st molten salt in the mixture and these values of u and P_i of mixtures lies in between the values of pure molten salts. In general, the computed values of density (ρ), thermal expansion coefficient (α), isothermal compressibility (β_T), adiabatic compressibility (β_S), heat capacity at constant pressure (C_p), heat capacities ratio (γ), pseudo-Gruneisen parameter (Γ) and non-linearity parameter (B/A) show a regular decreasing trend with increasing mole fraction of 1st component of the mixture. Heat capacity at constant volume (C_V) also shows a regular decreasing trend with mole fraction x_1 except NaCl + KCl, NaCl + RbCl and LiCl + KCl systems.

A close perusal of Table 4 show a better agreement between the experimental and theoretical values of aforementioned thermodynamic properties. The maximum deviation in the calculated values of ultrasonic velocity is -5.86% obtained in LiCl + CsCl system and the minimum deviation is -0.32%, obtain in the case of KCl + KBr system. The % deviation, in ultrasonic velocity (u), density (ρ), internal pressure (P_i), thermal expansion coefficient (α), isothermal compressibility (β_T), adiabatic compressibility (β_S), heat capacity at constant pressure (C_p), heat capacity at constant volume (C_V), heat capacities ratio (γ) and pseudo-Gruneisen parameter (Γ) are found to be below 3.5%, 1.0%, 6.5%, 1.0%, 5.5%, 5.0%, 4.0%, 5.5%, 1.0%, and 2.0% respectively for most of the systems.

Generally all the properties show the maximum deviation in case of LiCl + RbCl and LiCl + CsCl systems. This result shows that the deviation increase on increasing the non-ideality of the mixtures since the non-ideality increases on increasing the mass of cation of second component³². Thus, it may be concluded that Flory's theory can also be successfully applied in the case of binary molten salt mixtures.

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